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Correlates of Teaching Effectiveness of Faculty Members

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate and assess the teaching effectiveness of the faculty members in a private college in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. Respondents of this survey included 362 learners from various departments namely the College of Arts, Sciences and Education - Information Technology aptly called CASE-IT, College of Business, Management and Accountancy "CBMA," College of Engineering and Technology "CET," School of Medical Sciences "SMS," and School of Criminology "SOC." The researchers used frequency, mean, standard deviation, and chi-square as statistical tools. Mean and frequency were used in measuring the Age, Sex, and Department. Standard deviation was used to measure the extent of the scattered set of values. Chi-square was used in determining the significant relationship between the respondents' profile and their perspectives on teaching effectiveness. The mean was used for questions that require a five-point Likert Scale to assess their corresponding qualitative description. The findings of this study revealed that the learners perceived their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as very satisfactory in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning. Differences occurred in the learner's perspective in each department, revealing each strength and weakness in the faculty member's teaching effectiveness. Furthermore, the results imply that the faculty members' teaching effectiveness can be effectively enhanced by continuous professional development programs, peer observation programs, mentorship programs, recognition and appreciation of the faculty members, supportive leadership collaboration between the faculty members and administration, and promoting healthy work-life balance for the faculty members.

Keywords: *commitment, knowledge of subject, teaching for independent learning, management of learning*

Introduction

Effective learning requires effective teaching. Faculty members held a crucial role in guiding learners throughout their academic journey in higher education, significantly influencing the overall quality of education. Teaching was defined as "to cause to know something," "to guide the studies of," and "to impart knowledge of" (Merriam-Webster, Inc., 2018). In other words, teaching was a means of educating individuals to develop information or expertise while simultaneously affecting how one acted. Therefore, it implied that grasping faculty responsibility for the effectiveness of their teaching could be achieved primarily by demonstrating that learners possessed the appropriate knowledge or competence and by showing that the expected behavioral change was achieved. Thus, monitoring and evaluating faculty teaching effectiveness played an important role since it had a direct impact on how learners learned and encouraged ongoing development in the learning environment.

The educational process had a significant impact on the daily lives of learners. Understanding the characteristics of effective faculty members, as well as evaluating their teaching and management approaches, methods of communication, attitudes, and behaviors, was of utmost importance (Sakiz, 2016). Gupta and Verma (2021) stated that teaching effectiveness was primarily concerned with the interactions of teachers, their actions, the classroom setting, and how these affected students' learning. An effective teacher was termed an educator who possessed qualities such as emotional (kind, warm, compassionate), cognitive (using innovative teaching techniques, mastery of the subject), and behavioral competence (patient, punctual, attentive).

Learners were effective evaluators, and their perceptions of faculty members' teaching effectiveness had become more accurate and credible because of their actual experience in the classroom (Mohammed, 2021). As a result, the study sought to investigate the teaching effectiveness of faculty members at Aldersgate College Inc. as perceived by learners. A descriptive correlational research approach was used, as it was ideally suitable for investigating aspects and characteristics associated with faculty teaching effectiveness. The researchers observed a problem with faculty teaching effectiveness in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning, which notably affected faculty teaching effectiveness. This approach sought to provide a comprehensive understanding of how these variables influenced learners' overall educational experience and academic achievement at Aldersgate College Inc. Descriptive correlational research was employed to measure the extent of faculty teaching effectiveness.

Research Questions

The research aimed to investigate the teaching effectiveness of faculty members at Aldersgate College, Inc. from a learner's perspective, focusing on their commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning. The primary objective was to uncover how these factors impact learners' overall educational experience and academic success.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;

- 1.2. sex;
- 1.3. department?
2. What are the learners' perspectives on faculty members' teaching effectiveness in terms of the following indicators:
 - 2.1. commitment;
 - 2.2. knowledge of the subject;
 - 2.3. teaching for independent learning; and
 - 2.4. management of learning?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the learners' demographic profile variables and their perceived faculty members' teaching effectiveness?

Literature Review

Teaching effectiveness played a crucial role in education. Understanding learners' perspectives on faculty members' teaching effectiveness provided valuable insights into the dynamics of the teaching-learning process.

Effective teaching depended on different methodologies and the ability to help learners make progress. Skilled teachers applied their insight to help learners learn and flourish. They additionally encouraged learners to play an active role in their own education and development. Good classroom management empowered them to handle difficult subjects directly while introducing lessons in engaging ways that captured learners' interest and encouraged them to think deeply about the subjects. Experienced educators were enthusiastic about their subjects and used their knowledge to provide excellent learning opportunities (Hawthorne, 2022).

Studies had shown that learners' achievements were significantly influenced by the quality of teaching, yet comprehensive research guiding decisions regarding teacher hiring, retention, and promotion remained unresolved. However, empirical studies had identified key facets of teaching effectiveness. Firstly, teacher experience regularly had a positive impact on teacher effectiveness, especially during the first few years of teaching. Secondly, completing elite teacher preparation programs and earning advanced degrees, particularly in mathematics and science, seemed to improve learners' achievement, while data was less solid at the elementary level. Thirdly, certified teachers, particularly in important disciplines like mathematics, had a favorable influence on learners' results, but other qualifications had varying degrees of benefit. Fourthly, teacher coursework, which included pedagogical and subject-area training, improved teacher effectiveness, with content knowledge being especially important at the high school level.

The study by Ibad (2019) examined learners' perceptions of teacher effectiveness as a means to improve teaching in higher education. Ibad believed that specific strategies were required to enhance the quality of instruction. Learners' perceptions of teaching effectiveness were one measure of gauging teacher effectiveness. Other contributors to evaluating teaching effectiveness included evaluation by peers and examination of teaching portfolios, which were the work of professional bodies. Although what constituted teacher effectiveness as evident in teaching was debatable, several researchers had consensus on the characteristics that were hallmarks of good teaching. These hallmarks were expressed in the form of nine clear dimensions, namely interaction, rapport, extent of knowledge, clarity of expression, enthusiasm, learning, fair examination practices, manageable workload, and meaningful assignments. From another perspective, how learners perceived effective teaching exceeded the means of delivery and time. In this regard, contemporary learners considered certain characteristics to be indicative of effective teachers. These characteristics, derived from research on the subject, possessed universality in terms of when, where, what, and how of teaching. These attributes, numbering seven, included a sense of fair play, accessibility, receptiveness to new ideas, knowledge of the subject and pedagogy, the ability to see the lighter side, and inspiration through the teaching of the subject. These qualities were relevant to the research mission of universities and required plausible ways of measurement.

The study by Altun (2017) emphasized that teacher commitment was an integral component of high-quality education and a significant factor influencing the achievement of learners. Devoted educators committed their lives to their learners, the educational institution, and their chosen field of teaching. As a result, committed teachers had an impact on their learners' achievement and educational excellence, which helped teachers become more aware of the requirements of their learners. Additionally, Celik and Yildiz (2017) argued that a committed teacher would be passionate and enthusiastic about teaching and learning, which would ultimately have a direct impact on the learner's academic achievement and personal development.

According to Mangila (2022), a teacher's subject matter knowledge had a significant impact on the quality of education. Knowing one's subject matter implied mastery of one's discipline and the capacity to make use of available resources. Salandanan (2012) further stressed that for teachers to teach effectively, they must possess solid background knowledge of a particular subject area included in the learner's curriculum, be equipped with competence in deciding and implementing appropriate teaching methodologies, and possess a compassionate and winsome nature.

Moreover, the university teaching approach placed a strong emphasis on independent study as a means of instruction. Learners were expected to devote a significant amount of time to independent study. Examining undergraduate learners' study habits was especially important because universities largely depended on independent study as a fundamental part of their curricula. A full-time university learner typically studied for 40 hours a week, much of which was devoted to independent study, or studying outside of scheduled classroom environments (Butson et al., 2020). According to Esmaeili et al., (2018), teaching and learning management were essential

components of education and were defined as learning processes that took place under the supervision of the instructor. Additionally, Granada and Oco (2024)) argued that teachers were managers of their classrooms, and the educational institution was a unique organization whose effectiveness corresponded to the extent of the teacher's skill in various sectors, particularly personality. Teachers in classrooms should choose management styles suitable for their learners' personality characteristics and teaching methods so that learners could acquire an array of competencies through the educational process (Esmaeili et al., 2018).

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers employed quantitative research methodology, specifically descriptive correlational research design, to assess the teaching effectiveness of faculty members. This approach systematically gathers and examines data from various sources, primarily through surveys, to explore the relationships between different variables. The primary goal was to identify and evaluate faculty members' teaching effectiveness. Correlational research, a quantitative method, involves using two or more quantitative variables from the same set of individuals to explore potential connections.

Participants

The respondents of the study were 362 students from the various departments at Aldersgate College Inc., namely, CASE-IT, CBMA, CET, SMS, and SOC. The total population size of this study was 2,390 enrolled learners. Slovin formula was used to identify the ideal sample size based on the given population, and a stratified sampling technique was used to collect data from the respondents.

Instruments

In this study, the researchers used printed questionnaires and Google Forms to collect data. Therefore, the findings were limited to the information obtained from these instruments. The questionnaire was the learner evaluation for instructors, adopted from the tool used to rate the teaching effectiveness of instructors and professors at the institution. The adopted questionnaire was divided into two sections that helped the researchers achieve their objectives. The first section determined the respondents' profiles in terms of age, gender, and department. The second section was divided into four determinant factors: commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning.

The study used a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with descriptions ranging from poor to outstanding. The questionnaire allowed respondents to rate each variable on a five-point scale ranging from 4.51-5.0 (Outstanding), 3.51-4.50 (Very Satisfactory), 2.51-3.50 (Satisfactory), 1.51-2.50 (Fair), and 1.00-1.50 (Poor). This, in turn, provided information to help determine the learners' perception of faculty members' teaching effectiveness.

The instrument's reliability level was confirmed with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.9943, indicating excellent internal consistency. The questionnaire was piloted to 30 respondents to ensure its validity and reliability before being administered to the full sample.

To formulate the items on Part II of the questionnaire, the schema is presented as follows:

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>
Commitments	7 items
Knowledge of the Subject	7 items
Teaching for Independent Learning	7 items
Management of Learning	7 items
Total	28 items

Procedure

The researchers sought approval from the Vice President of Academic Affairs to use the institutional "Instrument for Teaching Effectiveness" as the survey tool. The questionnaire was piloted to 30 respondents to ensure its validity and reliability, achieving a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.99435, indicating excellent internal consistency. They also sought permission from the Office of the President of the institution to distribute the questionnaires to the respondents. Upon approval, the researchers requested the Deans of each department to allow their students to participate in the study. Additionally, the researchers obtained informed consent from the respondents, ensuring they understood the study's purpose and procedures.

After securing the necessary permissions, three hundred sixty-two students from different departments were selected using stratified sampling techniques to ensure representative participation. The researchers clarified the survey's instructions to all respondents to ensure accurate and honest responses. The data collected were then analyzed and interpreted by the researchers and served as the basis for conclusions and recommendations.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers prioritize ethical considerations to ensure the well-being and rights of the respondents. Firstly, they obtained informed consent from the respondents, ensuring they understood the study's purpose and procedures. Also, the respondents' privacy was

respected by securely storing their information and using encryption methods for online data collection. Furthermore, the respondents are all treated with dignity, allowing them to withdraw from the study without consequences. Additionally, the researchers are transparent about the research's goals and any potential conflict of interest and strive to minimize harm while maximizing benefits. Lastly, they have ensured compliance with ethical guidelines and regulations to conduct the study responsibly and ethically.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that the researchers gathered. The researchers have demonstrated the results in tables, analyzed them, and interpreted them to properly address the problems presented in this study using statistical analysis.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

<i>Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Age</i>		
<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
17-19 years old	83	22.9%
20-22 years old	228	63.0%
23-25 years old	33	9.1%
26 and above	18	5.0%
Total	362	100%
<i>Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Sex</i>		
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Female	245	67.7%
Male	117	32.3%
Total	362	100%
<i>Frequency and Percentage Distribution in terms of Department</i>		
<i>Department</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
CASE-IT	64	17.7%
CBMA	108	29.8%
CET	50	13.8%
SMS	54	14.9%
SOC	86	23.8%
Total	362	100%

The findings of the study in the profile variables of the respondent in terms of age, sex, and department revealed that the age group with the highest percentage, 63.0%, consists of those aged 20-22 years old, and the lowest, 5.0%, are those aged 26 and above. In terms of sex, there were 362 respondents, with 67.7% female and 32.3% male. Furthermore, the College of Business, Management, and Accountancy department has the largest percentage of respondents (29.8%), while the College of Engineering and Technology has the lowest (13.8%).

Summary of the Learners' Perspective on the Faculty Members' Teaching Effectiveness

Table 2. *Learner's Perspectives in Terms of Teacher's Commitment*

	<i>Commitment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Demonstrates sensitivity to learners' ability to clarify content formation	3.58	.84	Very Satisfactory
2.	Integrates sensitivity in his or her learning objectives in a collaborative process.	3.61	.81	Very Satisfactory
3.	Makes himself or herself available to learners beyond official time.	3.56	.90	Very Satisfactory
4.	Regularly comes to class on time and is well-prepared to complete assigned responsibilities.	3.64	.95	Very Satisfactory
5.	Keep accurate records of learners' performance and promptly submit them.	3.71	.87	Very Satisfactory
6.	Comes to class well-groomed and composed.	3.88	.91	Very Satisfactory
7.	Is articulate in communicating the subject matter and class expectations.	3.82	.89	Very Satisfactory
	General weighted mean	3.68		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

Table 2 presents the teaching effectiveness of faculty members as perceived by the learners in terms of commitment. The results show that the learners rated their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," with item 6 (Comes to class well-groomed and composed) receiving the highest mean of 3.88, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory," and item 1 (Demonstrates sensitivity to learners' ability to clarify content formation) obtains the lowest weight of 3.58, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory". However, across all questions asked among the learners, the results further indicate that the respondents have a moderate level of discrepancy between these perceptions as evidenced by the standard deviation; having item 4 (Regularly comes to class on time and is well-prepared to complete assigned responsibilities) has the highest standard deviation of .95 suggesting that learners perception vary the most on this aspect, with some learners possibly rating it very high and others rating it lower. Conversely, the aspect with the lowest standard deviation of .81 is item 2 (Integrates sensitivity in his or her learning objectives in a collaborative process) suggesting that learners' opinions are

more consistent on this aspect.

The preliminary results indicate that learners generally perceive their faculty members' commitment as very satisfactory, as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 3.68. Even though there is some variability in learners' perception as indicated by the standard deviations, the consistently high mean scores across all aspects suggest that faculty members are indeed committed and perform well in various aspects of their teaching. As Altun, M. (2017) emphasizes teacher commitment is an integral component of high-quality education and a significant factor influencing the achievement of learners. Devoted educators commit their lives to their learners, the educational institution, and their chosen field of teaching. As a result, committed teachers can have an impact on their learners' achievement and educational excellence, which helps teachers become more aware of the requirements of their learners. Additionally, Celik and Yildiz, (2017) argue that a committed teacher will be passionate and enthusiastic about teaching and learning, which will ultimately have a direct impact on the learner's academic achievement and personal development.

Table 3. *Learner's Perspectives in Terms of Knowledge of Subject*

	<i>Knowledge of Subject</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (i.e., explains the subject matter without relying solely on the prescribed textbook).	3.61	.96	Very Satisfactory
2.	Draws and shares information on the state-of-the-art theory and practice in his/her discipline.	3.74	.81	Very Satisfactory
3.	Integrates subject to practical circumstances and learning intents/purposes of learners	3.78	.82	Very Satisfactory
4.	Explains the relevance of present topics to the previous lessons and the broader aspect of the subject.	3.72	.83	Very Satisfactory
5.	Demonstrates up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness of current trends and issues of the subject.	3.79	.84	Very Satisfactory
6.	Presents the subject matter in a well-organized manner.	3.82	.82	Very Satisfactory
7.	Provides scholarly answers to questions raised on the subject during the ensuing discussions	3.79	.85	Very Satisfactory
General weighted mean		3.75		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

Table 3 presents the teaching effectiveness of faculty members as perceived by the learners in terms of knowledge of the subject. The results reveal that the learners perceived their faculty members' teaching effectiveness in terms of knowledge of the subject as "Very Satisfactory"; with item 6 (Presents the subject matter in a well-organized manner) garnering the highest mean of 3.82; and item 1 (Demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (i.e., explains the subject matter without relying solely on the prescribed textbook) with the lowest mean of 3.61, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory". The data also reveals that item 1 has the highest standard deviation of .96, indicating that while some learners may perceive the teacher's mastery of the subject matter positively, there is a significant variation in how other learners perceive it. Nonetheless, item 4 (Draws and shares information on the state-of-the-art theory and practice in his/her discipline) got the lowest standard deviation of .81 suggesting that learners' perspectives are more consistent on this aspect.

The preliminary results suggest that the learners' perceptions of their faculty members' teaching effectiveness in terms of knowledge of the subject were consistently rated as very satisfactory as evidenced by the general weighted mean of 3.75, with relatively low standard deviation values indicating little variability in the ratings. This suggests that the faculty members were highly regarded by the learners for their knowledge of the subject and their effective teaching methods. A related investigation undertaken by Mangila, B. B. (2022) strengthens the conclusions of this study, claiming that understanding the subject is extremely important because instructors must master the subjects they're supposed to instruct and acquire knowledge about how to educate these individuals so that learners can effectively comprehend their lessons. Moreover, Ilyas (2016) emphasizes that in order to ensure that learners understand the content more easily, teachers must be aware of how their learners think and how to teach them best. It has been discovered that teachers exhibiting greater experience in subject knowledge were able to make connections between their subject matter knowledge and the actual world. This, in turn, has been shown to improve the learning process for learners significantly.

Table 4 presents the teaching effectiveness of faculty members at Aldersgate College Inc. as perceived by the learners in terms of teaching for independent learning. The result shows that the learners perceived their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory", with the highest mean of 3.80, having item 3 (Allows learners to clarify courses with objectives and realistically defined learners-professor rules) while item 1 (Creates teaching strategies that allow learners to practice using concepts they need to understand (interactive discussion) received the lowest mean of 3.70, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory" suggest that these aspects slightly lower compared to others. Additionally, having item 4 (Allows learners to think independently and make their own decisions) with the highest standard deviation of .94 suggests that some learners may highly appreciate and value the opportunity to think independently while some may have their own learning styles. Having item 3 with the highest mean and the lowest standard deviation of .85 suggests that, overall, learners perceive this aspect of teaching for independent learning very positively. Even so, the standard deviation suggests that not all learners may have the same level of agreement or satisfaction with this aspect.

Table 4. *Learner's Perspectives in Terms of Teaching for Independent Learning*

<i>Teaching for Independent Learning</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Creates teaching strategies that allow learners to practice using concepts they need to understand (interactive discussion).	3.70	.90	Very Satisfactory
2.	Enhances learner's self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to learners' performance/potential.	3.74	.88	Very Satisfactory
3.	Allows learners to clarify courses with objectives and realistically defined learners-professor rules.	3.80	.85	Very Satisfactory
4.	Allows learners to think independently and make their own decisions.	3.78	.94	Very Satisfactory
5.	Is able to bring desirable and constructive changes in learners through instruction, example and influence.	3.79	.90	Very Satisfactory
6.	Allows learners to become accountable for their own performance.	3.79	.86	Very Satisfactory
7.	Guides the learners in the application of the concepts learned.	3.79	.87	Very Satisfactory
General weighted mean		3.77		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

The general weighted mean of 3.77 indicates that overall, the teaching for independent learning is viewed as very satisfactory by the learners. It can be concluded that the teaching strategies employed in terms of independent learning are effective in creating a positive learning environment. This claim is also supported by Ebata (2010) stating that increasing learners' autonomy is critical to producing successful learners. He believes that the three most crucial aspects for developing learners' autonomy are excellent material and teachers, a learners-centered cooperative learning environment, and meaningful skills teaching. He believes that self-directed learners will be more inspired to acquire knowledge. Moreover, the study by Agustina, D., and Fajar, D. A. (2019) proposes that independent learning includes: 1) individual effort to enhance language competency, 2) individuals' learning habits, 3) independent learning activities, 4) self-evaluation activity, and 5) self-reflection activity.

Table 5. *Learner's Perspectives on Terms of Management of Learning*

<i>Management of Learning</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	Creates opportunities for intensive and/ or extensive contribution of learners in the class activities (e.g., breaks the class into dyads, triads or buzz/task groups).	3.70	.87	Very Satisfactory
2.	Assumes roles as facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, integrator, and referee in drawing learners to contribute to knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hand.	3.78	.83	Very Satisfactory
3.	Designs and implements learning conditions and experiences that promote healthy exchange and/or argumentation/discourse.	3.75	.83	Very Satisfactory
4.	Structures/restructures learning and teaching-learning contexts to enhance the attainment of collective learning objectives.	3.73	.85	Very Satisfactory
5.	Uses instructional materials (audio/video materials, field trips, film showing, computer-aided instruction etc.) to reinforce the learning process.	3.81	.88	Very Satisfactory
6.	Maintains a clean and orderly classroom conducive to learning.	3.87	.92	Very Satisfactory
7.	Determines desired learning outcomes and objectively assesses learning performance within the allotted time.	3.81	.88	Very Satisfactory
General weighted mean		3.78		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

Table 5 presents the teaching effectiveness of faculty members at Aldersgate College Inc. as perceived by the learners in terms of the management of learning. The data reveal that the learners perceived their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," having item 6 (Maintains a clean and orderly classroom conducive to learning) receiving the highest mean of 3.87 which is interpreted as "Very Satisfactory" and item 1 (Creates opportunities for intensive and/ or extensive contribution of learners in the class activities (e.g., breaks class into dyads, triads or buzz/task groups) earning the lowest mean of 3.70, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory". However, having item 6 as the highest mean score among other aspects, it is important to note that it also has the highest standard deviation of .92, suggesting that there may be some learners who have higher expectations or different preferences regarding what constitutes a clean and orderly classroom. The standard deviation for both aspects is 0.83, having item 2 (Assumes roles as facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, integrator, and referee in drawing learners to contribute to knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hand) and item 3 (Designs and implements learning conditions and experiences that promote healthy exchange and/or argumentation/discourse), which is the lowest among all the aspects. It can be concluded that the learners' perspectives on these two aspects are relatively consistent, indicating general agreement among the learners in these areas.

As evidenced in the general weighted mean of 3.78, the preliminary results suggest that the faculty members' management of learning is very satisfactory from the learners' perspective. It also signifies that faculty members are effective in their teaching strategies and are successful in creating a positive and conducive learning environment. Teaching and learning management are essential components of education and are defined as learning processes that take place under the supervision of the instructor (Esmaeili et al., 2018). Additionally, Granada and Oco (2024) research argues that teachers are managers of their classrooms, and the educational institution

is a unique organization whose effectiveness corresponds to the extent of the teacher's skill in various sectors, particularly personality. Teachers in classrooms should choose styles of management that are suitable to their learners' personality characteristics and teaching methods so that learners can acquire an array of competencies through the educational process (Esmaeili et al., 2018).

Table 6. Summary of the Perception of the Learner's Perspective on Teaching Effectiveness

<i>Learner's Perspectives</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Commitment	3.69	.71	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge of Subject	3.76	.72	Very Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.77	.76	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.78	.72	Very Satisfactory
General weighted mean	3.75		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

Table 6 summarizes data on learners' perceptions of teaching effectiveness in four areas: commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning. The results of the study indicate that learners evaluated their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory" in four aspects and were significantly closer to one another, with management of learning receiving the highest mean score of 3.78, followed by teaching for independent learning with a mean of 3.77, knowledge of the subject with a mean of 3.76, and commitment receiving the lowest mean of 3.69. Further to that, the standard deviations for each aspect are minimal, ranging from .71 to .76. This implies that there is still some variation in the learners' perception of these aspects, indicating a high level of agreement.

The preliminary results show a very satisfactory outcome, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 3.75. The faculty members' commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning all have a positive impact on the learners' perceptions and are highly regarded. It provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of teaching from the learners' perspectives in a variety of areas. In the study of Hawthorne (2022), effective teaching using different approaches and the ability to encourage learners to make progress, Knowledgeable faculty members can use their experiences to help motivate learners to learn and thrive, as well as to play an active interest in their own education and development. Having effective classroom management allows them to manage complex concepts effectively, while also introducing lessons to capture aspects that engage learners and encourage them to think about the subject matter.

Learner's Perspective on the Faculty Member's Teaching Effectiveness in Various Departments

The results reveal that the CASE-IT learners perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," supported by a general weighted mean of 3.85. 'Teaching for independent learning' and 'management of learning' earned the highest weighted mean of 3.89, while 'knowledge of the subject' had the lowest mean of 3.80, all interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." These results suggest that the faculty members possess a high level of effectiveness in teaching for independent learning and managing learning environments. However, there is room for improvement in the area of 'knowledge of the subject.' While still considered "Very Satisfactory," the lower score of 3.80 indicates an opportunity for faculty to strengthen their subject matter expertise. Jain (2023) states that an educator's topic knowledge refers to an understanding and skill in the subject they are instructing, which is essential for effective teaching. Shulman (2021) also noted that most instructors are categorized as "Developing" or "Emerging" teachers, indicating a need for further development in subject expertise.

The CBMA learners perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," with a general weighted mean of 3.76. 'Knowledge of the subject' earned the highest weighted mean of 3.81, while 'teaching for independent learning' had the lowest mean of 3.72, all interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." These results indicate that the CBMA faculty members possess a high level of subject expertise. Learners' assessments show that their faculty members demonstrate mastery of the subject matter, share current theories and practices, integrate the subject into practical situations, and provide organized and relevant instruction. However, 'teaching for independent learning' scored the lowest mean at 3.72. Barbosa et al. (2017) stated that higher education curricula typically require significant independent study. Susanti (2017) found mixed opinions on independent learning, highlighting its benefits for some learners and challenges for others.

The CET learners perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," supported by a general weighted mean of 3.96. 'Teaching for independent learning' and 'management of learning' both earned the highest weighted mean of 3.99, while 'knowledge of the subject' had the lowest mean of 3.80, all interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." Similar to the CASE-IT results, CET learners perceive their faculty members as teaching effectively, especially in fostering independent learning and managing learning environments. However, there is room for improvement in faculty members' knowledge of the subject. Shulman (2021) emphasized that a strong foundation in subject matter is crucial for effective teaching and overall success.

The SMS learners perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Satisfactory," with a general weighted mean of 3.50. 'Management of learning' earned the highest weighted mean of 3.56, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory," while 'commitment' garnered the lowest mean of 3.40, interpreted as "Satisfactory." These results reveal that SMS faculty members excel in managing learning environments. However, 'commitment' is identified as an area needing improvement. Mgonja and Makulilo (2022) highlighted the impact of commitment on teaching effectiveness, suggesting that enhancing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation could address issues

related to faculty commitment.

Table 7. Learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness per Department

<i>CASE-IT learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness</i>			
<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Commitment	3.82	.69	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge of the Subject	3.80	.71	Very Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.89	.71	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.89	.69	Very Satisfactory
General Weighted Mean	3.85		Very Satisfactory
<i>CBMA learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness</i>			
Commitment	3.73	.80	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge of Subject	3.81	.87	Very Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.72	.95	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.78	.86	Very Satisfactory
General Weighted Mean	3.76		Very Satisfactory
<i>CET learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness</i>			
Commitment	3.93	.61	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge of Subject	3.91	.64	Very Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.99	.58	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.99	.60	Very Satisfactory
General Weighted Mean	3.96		Very Satisfactory
<i>SMS learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness</i>			
Commitment	3.40	.62	Satisfactory
Knowledge of Subject	3.47	.54	Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.55	.66	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.56	.54	Very Satisfactory
General Weighted Mean	3.50		Satisfactory
<i>SOC learners' Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness</i>			
Commitment	3.69	.65	Very Satisfactory
Knowledge of Subject	3.75	.61	Very Satisfactory
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.76	.65	Very Satisfactory
Management of Learning	3.74	.67	Very Satisfactory
General Weighted Mean	3.74		Very Satisfactory

Note: 1-1.50=Poor, 1.51-2.50=Fair, 2.51-3.50=Satisfactory, 3.51-4.50=Very Satisfactory, 4.51-5=Outstanding

The SOC learners perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness as "Very Satisfactory," with a general weighted mean of 3.74. 'Teaching for independent learning' earned the highest weighted mean of 3.76, while 'commitment' had the lowest mean of 3.69, all interpreted as "Very Satisfactory." Similar to the results from CASE-IT and CET, SOC learners perceive their faculty members as effective in teaching for independent learning.

Correlation Analysis of the Profile of the Respondents in their Perspective in Teaching Effectiveness

Table 8. Correlation Analysis of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age and Teaching Effectiveness

	<i>Chi-square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>Decision</i>
Commitment	78.277	.208	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Knowledge of Subject	84.016	.105	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Teaching for Independent Learning	78.945	.355	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Management of Learning	61.031	.439	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Note: If the p-value is greater than 0.05, there is no significant relationship between variables, and we accept the hypothesis. If the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship, and we reject the hypothesis.

Table 8 reveals data from the significant relationship between respondents' ages and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in various aspects. For commitment, the chi-square value is 78.277 with a p-value of 0.208, indicating that we accept the null hypothesis and conclude that there is no significant relationship between respondents' age and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of commitment given the p-value is greater than 0.05. Similarly, for the knowledge of the subject, the chi-square value is 84.016, and the p-value is 0.105. The p-value is greater than 0.05, signifying that there is no significant relationship between respondents' age and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of knowledge of the subject. Teaching for independent learning has a chi-square value of 78.945 and a p-value of 0.355. The p-value is greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no relationship between respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of teaching for independent learning. Furthermore, for the management of learning, the chi-square value is 61.031 with a p-value of 0.439, showing that there is no significant relationship between respondents' age and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of management of learning, given the p-value greater than the significance level.

According to the findings, there is no significant relationship between the respondents' age and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness. All of the p-values for all of the different indicators of teaching effectiveness are greater than the .05 significance level, which means that we cannot reject the H_0 , and it is evident that respondents' age does not affect their perception of teaching effectiveness. However, in the study of Sprinkle J. (2009), it was found that the learners' perceptions of educator effectiveness were significantly influenced by learner biases in areas such as gender, age, teaching style, learning style, grade awarded, and educator personality. Moreover, age and seniority are both found to negatively affect the students' evaluation of teaching effectiveness (Bianchini et al., 2013).

Table 9. *Correlation Analysis of the Profile of Respondents in Terms of Sex and Teaching Effectiveness*

	Chi-square	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Commitment	14.538	.910	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Knowledge of Subject	33.911	.066	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Teaching for Independent Learning	27.874	.314	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Management of Learning	35.384	.018	Significant	Reject H_0

Note: If the p-value is greater than 0.05, there is no significant relationship between variables, and we accept the hypothesis. If the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship, and we reject the hypothesis.

Table 9 shows a significant relationship between the respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness. The chi-square value is 14.538, with a p-value of 0.910 for commitment. Given that the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result is not statistically significant and accepts the null hypothesis. The chi-square value for knowledge of the subject is 33.911, with a p-value of 0.066. It shows that the p-value is greater than 0.05, showing that there is no significant relationship between respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of knowledge of the subject. The chi-square value is 27.874, with a p-value of 0.314 for teaching independent learning. The p-value is greater than 0.05, suggesting that the outcome is not statistically significant, and there is no relationship between respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of teaching for independent learning. However, for the management of learning, the chi-square value is 35.384, and the p-value is 0.018. The p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant result. This shows that there is a significant relationship between the sex of the respondents and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of the management of learning.

The results of the study reveal that there is no significant relationship between respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject, and teaching for independent learning given that their p-values are greater than the .05 significance level, so we cannot reject the hypothesis. On the other hand, there is a significant relationship between respondents' sex and their perceptions of teaching effectiveness in terms of management of learning, as revealed by the p-values which is less than 0.05; thus, we accept the H_0 . Moreover, in the study of Lavin et al. (n.d.), it was found that there are no statistically significant differences in the ranking order between female and male learners when assessing the factor identified as having the greatest and least impact on effective teaching.

Table 10. *Correlation of the Profile of Respondents in Terms of Department and Teaching Effectiveness*

	Chi-square	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Commitment	14.538	.910	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Knowledge of Subject	33.911	.066	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Teaching for Independent Learning	27.874	.314	Not Significant	Accept H_0
Management of Learning	35.384	.018	Significant	Reject H_0

Note: If the p-value is greater than 0.05, there is no significant relationship between variables, and we accept the hypothesis. If the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship, and we reject the hypothesis.

Table 10 shows a significant relationship in respondents' perceptions of faculty members' teaching effectiveness based on their department. The chi-square values were 119.588, 148.033, 143.116, and 125.947, with P-values of .028, .0001, .003, and .0001 for Commitment, Knowledge of the Subject, Teaching for Independent Learning, and Management Learning, correspondingly. This demonstrates that all indicators of teaching effectiveness are less than the significance level of 0.05. As a result, we reject H_0 's claim and conclude that there is a significant relationship between respondents' departments and their perceptions of faculty members' teaching effectiveness.

Conclusion

The majority of the respondents are female and aged 20 to 22. Most were from the College of Business, Management, and Accountancy.

The researchers concluded that each department has its own strengths and weaknesses in the four key aspects of teaching effectiveness. This means that each department may excel in some areas while showing room for improvement in others. Specifically, the learners' perspectives on faculty members' teaching effectiveness in CASE-IT, CBMA, CET, and SOC were very satisfactory, suggesting that the learners perceived their faculty members in these departments to be highly effective in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning. On the other hand, SMS department students rated their faculty

members' teaching effectiveness as satisfactory. While this may imply that faculty members in this department are regarded as effective by learners, it also shows that there is still opportunity for growth to fulfill the learners' needs and expectations better. Overall, the data show that, while learners have generally positive perspectives of faculty members' teaching effectiveness across departments, there is a need for improvement in the SMS department.

The researchers concluded that there is no significant relationship between the profile variables of age and learners' perceptions of faculty members' teaching effectiveness. This suggests that age does not influence how learners assess faculty members' effectiveness in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject, teaching for independent learning, and management of learning. Similarly, the researchers concluded that sex has no significant relationship between sex in most aspects of teaching effectiveness. This suggests that sex has no significant influence on how learners perceive the faculty members' commitment, knowledge of the subject, and teaching for independent learning. The data revealed no significant correlation between sex and each of these aspects of teaching effectiveness, except for a significant relationship in the management of learning. It also suggests that sex may influence how students view faculty members' effectiveness in the management of learning. On the other hand, the researchers concluded that there is a significant relationship between respondents' departments and learners' perceptions of faculty members' teaching effectiveness. The department to which learners belong has an important influence on how they perceive their faculty members' teaching effectiveness.

Based on the aforementioned findings and conclusion the following recommendations are presented (1) The study shows that the learners view the faculty members' teaching effectiveness as very satisfactory. To improve further, the school should continue to encourage and help faculty members keep up with new knowledge and techniques in their field, improve their teaching skills and course materials, and continue their professional growth through Faculty Development. These programs include adequate and qualified supervision of faculty, scholarships, sabbatical leaves, and/or research grants, financial support for attendance at continuing professional development (CPD) programs such as research-related activities, seminars, workshops, and conferences, in-service training courses, periodic faculty meetings, and participation in faculty committees. (2) In a follow-up study, future researchers could broaden the study's scope encompassing the entire institutional landscape. It is recommended that future studies ensure gender parity in respondent selection to facilitate a more comprehensive understanding of teaching effectiveness, considering potential gender differences in perception. By expanding the scope and ensuring inclusivity, future research can contribute to enhancing teaching practices and enriching academic discourse. (3) It is recommended that rigorous parallel investigations can be conducted to acquire a broader understanding of faculty members' effectiveness in teaching and their job performance. These investigations can involve the use of alternative data collection methods such as classroom observations, individual interviews, and focus group discussions. To enhance the comprehensiveness of the study, it is crucial to include the number of years in service of faculty members for a broader insight into the relationship between experience and teaching effectiveness. In addition, it is essential to consider the inclusion of minor and major subjects by examining faculty member's strengths and weaknesses in different subject areas. Therefore, further research is strongly encouraged to provide a more comprehensive understanding of faculty members' teaching effectiveness and job performance.

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